

WHO IS THE CORRUPT ONE? TEACHING ENGLISH RELATIVE CLAUSES THROUGH CORRUPTION-RELATED VOCABULARY

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Abstract

To clearly and effectively communicate ideas in English, learners of both General English and English for Specific Purposes (ESP) should be able to use relative clauses correctly. Relative clauses serve as the building blocks for syntactically complex sentences expressing relationships between different sentence parts. Through appropriate use of relative clauses, learners can achieve a higher level of precision of expression when using the language both orally and in writing. This can eliminate possible misunderstandings, which is particularly important in specific contexts and professional settings, including that of law enforcement.

In the English for law enforcement classroom, relative clauses can be taught through many topics covered by this field, one of which is corruption. As an increasingly topical issue, it has led to the creation of an extensive vocabulary linked to corruption-related concepts that law-enforcement learners need to understand. Therefore, the paper will examine the semantic features and nuanced meanings of selected vocabulary related to corruption and will present suggestions for its inclusion in classroom activities tailored for teaching relative clauses. Through their practical implementation in the English classroom, the learners will enhance their knowledge and use of relative clauses while simultaneously acquiring corruption-related vocabulary.

Keywords: English language, relative clauses, corruption-related vocabulary, classroom activities

1. INTRODUCTION

Developing grammatical competence is a vital part of the English language learning process. Proficiency in constructing grammatically correct sentences enables the learners to express their thoughts accurately in various contexts and domains. This, among other things, encompasses learners' mastery of the rules behind the formation of relative clauses. The learners' ability to use relative clauses correctly is a major indicator of their overall knowledge of the language itself, considering the role relative clauses play within the sentences they are part of. Relative clauses help learners organize their thoughts in larger sentences, clarifying them by adding either crucial or additional information about sentence parts. Also, they can be used for joining several sentences into one, thus contributing to a smoother flow and greater clarity and precision of expression. This is particularly relevant when using English in a written form, especially when the speakers want to raise the formality level of their texts, which equally applies to professional and non-professional settings.

Law enforcement is one of the domains in which using relative clauses can improve communication clarity, especially in written texts, such as reports, requests, legal documents, communication with the public and the media, etc. This applies to using the language in all areas connected with law enforcement and crimes, including corruption. Thus, for instance, in an incident report, saying that a) *The police officers interviewed a woman*, is a very general statement lacking the details that more specifically define the woman in question, compared to the improved version b) *The police officers interviewed a woman who had witnessed the corruption scandal* in which the woman who was interviewed was that specific one who had witnessed a corruption scandal. In addition, other information about the woman would describe the situation even more clearly, so we may say that c) *The police officers, who had extensive experience in solving economic crimes, interviewed a woman who had witnessed the corruption scandal*, etc.

As the example above suggests, law enforcement professionals may prevent possible misunderstandings by providing details, either essential or non-essential, introduced by corresponding relative clauses. Misunderstandings may occur if, for instance, the relative clauses are not properly used or marked within a longer sentence. For example, if we say a) *A man saw the woman with the bribe money who argued with the police officers*, it may not be clear who the person who argued with the police officer is – the man, or the woman. Therefore, if that person is the man, the correct sentence would be b) *A man, who argued with the police officers, saw the woman with the bribe money*, but if the person who argued with the police officers is the woman, the appropriate version would be c) *A man saw the woman with the bribe money, who argued with the police officers*. Another cause of misunderstanding in law enforcement contexts may be the incorrect placement of the relative clause when modifying a given headword. Thus, for example, if the relative clause is not placed adjacent to the headword it modifies, the sentence will acquire a completely different meaning (Ajero, O.M., 2025:3870). For instance, if we say 1) *The policeman whom the old woman had accused of corruption attacked the journalist*, the relative pronoun *whom the old woman had accused of corruption* refers to the policeman – its headword, and the rest of the sentence tells us that the police officer in question attacked the journalist. But, if we change the location of the relative clause, and say 2) *The policeman attacked the journalist whom the old woman had accused of corruption*, the relative clause is attached to a wrong headword (*the journalist*), and now the journalist becomes the one accused of corruption, which is totally unrelated to the original correct sentence.

Therefore, avoiding misunderstandings and ambiguities is of crucial importance in law enforcement contexts, given the importance of details and accuracy in providing descriptions and detailed information of various kinds communicated by law enforcement officers daily. The lack of accuracy and attention to details may lead to far-reaching consequences of legal or other nature for any party affected by the content of the texts in question. For this reason, in the sections that follow we will discuss the link between relative clauses and the topic of corruption, with specific ideas about integrating relative clauses in English language instruction focused on topics connected with corruption.

2. RELATIVE CLAUSES IN ENGLISH AND THEIR USE IN CORRUPTION-RELATED CONTEXTS

Relative clauses are a type of subordinate clauses. They typically describe the noun or the noun phrase they are preceded by, giving information about them, either essential or non-essential. When referring to nouns or noun phrases, they are generally classified as: 1) defining relative clauses, or 2) non-defining relative clauses.

Defining relative clauses give information about the noun they refer to “in such a way to distinguish it from other nouns of the same class” (Thomson & Martinet, 1986:81). Therefore, a defining relative clause “is essential to the clear understanding of the noun” (ibid), and must not be omitted, since its omission will affect the understanding of the noun in question due to the loss of the crucial information which defines it. For instance, if we say that 1) *The woman left the country*, the noun *woman* may refer to any woman in general. However, if we say that 2) *The woman who misappropriated the state funds left the country*, the reference to the woman in question is clear. In this case, it is the defining relative clause *who misappropriated the state funds* which provided this essential information about the noun. Defining relative clauses can also be used after pronouns, especially indefinite ones, such as *anyone*, *everyone*, and *everything* (Sinclair et al., 1997:363), like in the sentence *Anyone who breaks the law will be punished*. Defining relative clauses are also called restrictive relative clauses. Non-defining relative clauses, on the other hand, give additional information which is non-essential and can be omitted without affecting the meaning of the entire sentence. Thus, for instance, we can say that 3) *My neighbour Maria, whose daughter lives abroad, misappropriated the state funds*, where the relative clause *whose daughter lives abroad* gives us information about the country of residence of Maria’s daughter, which is totally irrelevant in this context. We can delete this clause, and we will still know who the person is. This is an example of a non-defining relative clause, which is always inserted between two commas or dashes, and is also called a non-restrictive relative clause. In some cases, relative clauses can even modify sentence parts or entire sentences. When used with this function, they are referred to as sentential relative clauses (Aarts, Chalker & Weiner, 2014:359), or connective clauses (Thomson & Martinet, 1986:88).

Relative clauses are introduced by relative pronouns. The typical relative pronouns referring to people are *who* and *that* (e.g. *The police arrested the politician who/that received bribe*), while those referring to objects are *which* and *that* (e.g. *The police found the money which/that was extorted from the local businessman.*). In non-defining relative clauses, only *which* can be used. As object of the relative clause, one can use the pronoun *whom*, as well as *who* and *that* (Sinclair et al., 1997:364). Thus, we can say *The woman whom/who/that Steve had blackmailed reported him to the police*, where the relative pronoun is the object of the verb *blackmail*. Possession for both people and things is expressed with *whose* (E.g. *I saw the man whose son was involved in the grand corruption scandal in our city; This is the woman whose safe was used to hide the embezzled money.*). Additionally, *where* can act as a relative pronoun denoting location (E.g. *This is the place where the corrupt official was caught with the stolen money.*), *when* for denoting time (E.g. *The suspect provided an alibi for the day when the money was stolen from the company safe*), etc.

With reference to corruption-related issues, relative clauses can be used in various situations, both in writing and in speech. Generally speaking, relative clauses in law-enforcement contexts, including the area of corruption, can be used for: a) describing persons (e.g. *The man who embezzled the funds fled the country*); b) describing objects

(e.g. *The suitcase which contained the counterfeited banknotes was found in a black car at the border crossing*); c) describing places (e.g. *The building where the fake credit cards were hidden is located on the outskirts of the city*), etc. Also, examples of relative clauses can be found in many written documents addressing the issue of corruption. Thus, for example, in Transparency International Corruption Perception Index 2024, we can read that “corruption can also deepen the marginalisation of vulnerable populations who suffer disproportionately from the negative effects of climate change” (Transparency International, 2025a:6). Also, in an OSCE Report we can read that “the OSCE’s efforts to combat corruption and promote good governance are an integral part of its comprehensive approach to security, which encompasses politico-military, economic and environmental, and human dimensions” (OSCE, 2024:4). In addition, in a UNODC (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime) report we can read that “individuals who expose corrupt practices in their workplace or work environment play an essential role in a country’s anti-corruption efforts” (UNODC, 2024:36), etc.

3. RELATIVE CLAUSES THROUGH CORRUPTION-RELATED VOCABULARY IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE CLASSROOM

Taking into consideration the relevance of the knowledge of correctly using relative clauses in the domain of law enforcement, in this section we will propose several ideas for teaching relative clauses of both types (defining and non-defining), while simultaneously introducing selected vocabulary associated with corruption, based on pair work and group work.

3.1. Sample Activity 1: Types of Corruption

When learning about corruption, it is of high importance for law enforcement students to be able to distinguish between different types of corruption in terms of their specific elements, similarities and differences. Considering this, we suggest an activity in which the students work in groups and are given the task to fill in missing sentence parts in definitions of several types of corruption. All missing parts from the definitions contain relative clauses. The definitions are taken from the website of Transparency International. This activity is aimed at practising the use of both defining and non-defining relative clauses.

The following is an excerpt from this sample activity:

Missing sentence parts:

- 1) *who abuse their position to sustain their power, status and wealth*
- 2) *who often are trying to access basic goods or services in places like hospitals, schools, police departments and other agencies*
- 3) *that benefits the few at the expense of the many, and causes serious and widespread harm to individuals and society*

1. PETTY CORRUPTION

Everyday abuse of entrusted power by public officials in their interactions with ordinary citizens,

.....

Key:

Everyday abuse of entrusted power by public officials in their interactions with ordinary

citizens, who often are trying to access basic goods or services in places like hospitals, schools, police departments and other agencies. (Transparency International, 2025c)

Vocabulary in focus:

abuse of entrusted power
public official

2.GRAND CORRUPTION

The abuse of high-level power.....
It often goes unpunished.

Key:

The abuse of high-level power that benefits the few at the expense of the many, and causes serious and widespread harm to individuals and society. It often goes unpunished. (ibid, 2025b)

Vocabulary in focus:

abuse of high-level power
benefit
harm to individuals and society

3.POLITICAL CORRUPTION

Manipulation of policies, institutions and rules of procedure in the allocation of resources and financing by political decision makers,

Key:

Manipulation of policies, institutions and rules of procedure in the allocation of resources and financing by political decision makers, who abuse their position to sustain their power, status and wealth. (ibid, 2025d)

Vocabulary in focus:

manipulation of policies, institutions, rules and procedures
allocation of resources
to abuse one’s position
to sustain one’s power, status and wealth

As a follow-up activity, students can be asked to work in pairs, find the definitions of other types of corruption, remove the relative clauses, and work with their partners filling up the missing parts and discussing the relative clause in question and the corruption-related vocabulary the definition contains. The list with other types of corruption may include the following: ***endemic corruption, public corruption, corporate corruption, systemic corruption***, etc.

3.2. Sample Activity 2: Nepotism vs. Cronyism

Nepotism and cronyism are widely invoked concepts in the study of corruption. However, many English language learners, including those specializing in law enforcement, struggle to differentiate between them. For that reason, we suggest an activity where the students, working in pairs, are given jumbled sentences. They should rearrange the words to form the original sentences, which should contain non-defining relative clauses. This activity is aimed at practising specifically the use of non-defining relative clauses.

The following is an excerpt from this sample activity:

Example 1:

(favorising power the nepotism of is family the meritocracy one's opposite of position refers to which members of own using)

Key:

Nepotism, which is the opposite of meritocracy, refers to favouring members of one's own family using the position of power.

Example 2:

(awarding which in cronyism meant is to friends by power advantages originally those "friendship")

Key:

Cronyism, which originally meant "friendship", is awarding advantages to friends by those in power.

As a follow-up activity, the students can be given definitions of other -ISMS related to corruption, and they should work in groups and insert non-defining relative clauses to add more information about the words in question. This could encompass -ISMS such as *favouritism*, which refers to "unfair support shown to one person or group, especially by someone in authority" (Cambridge Dictionary, 2025b), *clientelism*, which means "a political or social system based on the relation of client to patron with the client giving political or financial support to a patron (as in the form of votes) in exchange for some special privilege or benefit" (Merriam-Webster Dictionary, 2025), etc.

3.3. Sample Activity 3: Acronyms

The English language abounds in acronyms, especially those denoting organizations, institutions, and documents addressing corruption-related issues. This makes acronyms a necessary part of English language instruction in the field of law enforcement. With this in mind, we suggest an activity in which the students are distributed a list of acronyms related to corruption. They should work in pairs and try to find the meanings of the acronyms. When they finish, each pair presents the meanings of the acronyms, using a relative clause in describing their meanings and what they refer to. This activity is aimed at practising the use of defining and non-defining relative clauses.

The following is an excerpt from this sample activity:

List of corruption-related acronyms:

GRECO (Group of States Against Corruption)

FATF (Financial Action Task Force)

TI (Transparency International)

UNCAC (United Nations Convention Against Corruption)

OLAF (European Anti-Fraud Office (Office européen de lutte antifraude))

DCAF (Democratic Control of Armed Forces (now formally known as DCAF – Geneva Centre for Security Sector Governance))

Example:

OLAF

OLAF is the acronym which refers to the European Anti-Fraud Office. OLAF, which was established in 1999, investigates cases of fraud, corruption and other criminal acts within the EU institutions...

As a follow-up activity, students can work in pairs to find other acronyms related to corruption and present their meanings to the class, inserting non-defining relative clauses in their explanations, whenever possible.

3.4. Sample Activity 4: Crimes Related to Corruption

Since acts of corruption are central to the commission of many crimes, we suggest an activity in which the students work in groups and are given a list with crimes rooted in corruption. One student should look up the meanings of the crimes and write two sentences which define them. The other students should join the two sentences for each crime into one, using the appropriate relative pronoun. This activity is aimed at practising the use of all relative pronouns.

The following is an excerpt from this sample activity:

List of crimes:

influence peddling

abuse of discretionary powers

breach of official duty

misuse of public resources

Example 1:

influence peddling

Trading in influence refers to the illegal activity of a politician doing something for somebody in return for payment. (Oxford Learner's Dictionaries, 2025b)

It is also called trading in influence.

Key:

Influence peddling, which is also called trading in influence, refers to the illegal activity of a politician doing something for somebody in return for payment.

As a follow-up activity students may work in groups to browse the Criminal Code of their country and make a list of crimes which are rooted in corruption with two sentences describing each crime. They should then work together to join the sentences into one, following the analogy in the presented classroom activity.

3.5. Sample Activity 5: Ethic(s) vs. Integrity

The concepts of ethic(s) and integrity, both related to corruption, are often used interchangeably by English language learners, despite their semantic differences. For that reason, in this section we suggest a classroom exercise where the students will be able to make a distinction between them. The students are given definitions of the nouns *ethic(s)* and *integrity*. For instance, *ethic*, typically used in plural as *ethics*, could be defined as “moral principles that control or influence a person’s behaviour” (Oxford Learner’s Dictionaries, 2025a), or “a system of accepted beliefs that control behaviour, especially such a system based on morals” (Cambridge Dictionary, 2025a). On the other hand, *integrity* could be defined as “the quality of being honest and having strong moral principles” (Oxford Learner’s Dictionaries, 2025c), “the quality of being honest and having strong moral principles that you refuse to change” (Cambridge Dictionary, 2025b), etc. After the introductory discussion on the comparison of these two concepts, the students are given several sentences where the missing words are either *ethic(s)* or *integrity*. They should work in pairs and try to guess and insert the missing word in each sentence. This activity is aimed at practising the use of defining relative clauses with *which/that*.

The following is an excerpt from this activity:

- 1) is a term WHICH is associated with persons (Key: *INTEGRITY*)
- 2) is a concept WHICH is broader in scope (Key: *ETHIC(S)*)
- 3) is a noun WHICH can be used with the following verbs: to compromise, to undermine, to question (Key: *INTEGRITY*)
- 4) is a noun WHICH is usually used in plural (Key: *ETHIC(S)*)

As a follow-up activity, students may be given a task to find other pairs of words which refer to similar concepts and may possibly be confusing for them. They should study the meanings of those pairs of words and write short paragraphs in which they will explain their differences, using the appropriate relative pronouns. Word pairs of this type in the context of corruption may include the following: *corruption* and *bribery*, *extortion* and *blackmail*, *fraud* and *scam*, etc.

3.6. Sample Activity 6: Easily confused words related to corruption

English terminology in the field of corruption contains many words that might cause confusion among speakers, because of the similarity in their pronunciation, the common root they are derived from, the same words they collocate with, etc. One example of this is the adjectives *corrupt*, *corruptive* and *corruptible*, which share the same root but denote three characteristics of persons, situations, things etc. In this activity the students will learn to differentiate between these three adjectives, while practising the use of the relative pronouns *who*, *which* and *that*. For this purpose, they will be given a gapped text in

which these three adjectives are described. The students should work in groups and insert the missing relative pronouns and adjectives to form meaningful sentences. This activity is aimed at practising the use of defining clauses with *who*, *which* and *that*.

The following is an excerpt from this activity:

CORRUPT, CORRUPTIVE or CORRUPTIBLE?

A person is may possibly be corrupted. Behaviours, situations, circumstances, etc. have the potential to lead to corruption are referred to as A person is has a history of corruption-related practices.

Key:

A person WHO is CORRUPTIBLE may possibly be corrupted. Behaviours, situations, circumstances, etc. WHICH/THAT have the potential to lead to corruption are referred to as CORRUPTIVE. A person WHO is CORRUPT has a history of corruption-related practices.

As a follow-up, students may work in pairs and try to find other words which, for instance, are derived from the same root, analyse their meanings, similarities, differences and contexts of use and then present their findings to the other students in the class. The list may include adjectives such as *bribed* and *briable*, for instance, and many other words.

3.7. Sample Activity 7: Authentic Documents with Relative Clauses

When performing their duties, law-enforcement professionals will handle many documents of authentic nature, often in other languages, including English. Therefore, English language instruction should include use of such documents in which the learners will be able to acquire both grammar and lexical knowledge in the field. To illustrate this, in this section we suggest an activity in which the students are given excerpts from an authentic document, in this specific example GRECO's 2024 report titled: *Anti-corruption Trends, Challenges and Good Practices in Europe & the United States of America* (Council of Europe, 2025), from the section addressing corruption prevention in law enforcement agencies. The students should work in pairs, find sentences which contain relative clauses and separate them into two sentences, eliminating the relative pronouns. This activity is aimed at practising the use of defining and non-defining relative clauses with *which* and *whose*.

The following is an excerpt from this activity:

Example 1) Policy on gifts applicable in the Police – Lithuania

“Lithuania established a policy on Gifts applicable in the Lithuanian Police and set up a Gifts Register and an Illegal Remuneration Register in the Police Department Management System. The policy sets out gifts valuation criteria, rules and thresholds on acceptable gifts, as well as their register, WHICH is public and is updated regularly.” (Council of Europe, 2025:20)

Key:

1. *The policy sets out gifts valuation criteria, rules and thresholds on acceptable gifts, as well as their register.*
2. *The register is public and is updated regularly.*

Vocabulary in focus:

a policy on Gifts

Gifts Register

Illegal Remuneration Register

gifts valuation criteria

thresholds on acceptable gifts

Example 2) **Recording and evaluating gifts – Serbia**

“A Commission for the Registration of Gifts, established in 2021 within the Ministry of the Interior, and WHOSE members are appointed by the Minister for a period of three years, is responsible, in particular, for maintaining records of gifts received and their disposal.” (ibid)

Key:

1. *A Commission for the Registration of Gifts, established in 2021 within the Ministry of the Interior, responsible, in particular, for maintaining records of gifts received and their disposal.*
2. *The members of this Commission are appointed by the Minister for a period of three years.*

“In January 2022, the Instruction of the Minister of the Interior lowered the threshold of admissible gifts to not more than 10% of the average monthly salary in Serbia, which is a very significant reduction from the previously existing permissible threshold.” (ibid)

Key:

1. *In January 2022, the Instruction of the Minister of the Interior lowered the threshold of admissible gifts to not more than 10% of the average monthly salary in Serbia.*
2. *This is a very significant reduction from the previously existing permissible threshold.*

Vocabulary in focus:

A Commission for the Registration of Gifts

maintaining records of gifts

threshold of admissible gifts

As a follow-up activity, students may work in pairs to find laws in their country which address the issue of corruption, identify and make a list of sentences containing relative clauses. After that, they should give the sentences to other pairs of students in the class and ask them to split the long sentences into two or more parts, by eliminating the relative pronouns and inserting the appropriate changes to form grammatically correct sentences.

CONCLUSION

The activities detailed in the paper lead to the conclusion that it is possible to teach relative clauses in English via presentation of corruption-related vocabulary and vice versa. This can be accomplished through interactive classroom activities based on pair and group work. The activities described in the paper focused on the differences between various corruption types, the meanings of different acronyms related to corruption, the peculiarities of certain crimes rooted in corruption, the difference between similar and confusing words associated with corruption, the practical use of relative clauses in authentic documents addressing corruption-related issues, etc. However, they can be modified and adapted for teaching other grammatical structures and specialized vocabulary in law enforcement or other domains. Furthermore, they can be used for teaching specialized law enforcement content from other subjects, with appropriate adaptations.

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